

THE ROLE OF THE ACTIVITIES OF THE NATIONAL SEGMENT IN DEMOCRATIC PROCESSES THROUGH THE INTERNET CYBERSPACE

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Abstract. The article discusses the activities of the national segment of the Internet in the era of informatization of society and analyzes the results of their activities. At the same time, through sociological research, the problems of developing information resources in the national segment of the Internet are identified, and a number of factors that affect the efficiency of filling the site with relevant materials are provided with systematized analysis.

Key words: information security, public opinion, national segment, national sites, survey, information space, site, social networks, online journalism, design, interactivity.

Аннотация. Мақолада рақамли жамиятда миллий сегмент фаолияти ўрганилган ва натижалар таҳлил қилинган. Шу билан бирга, глобал интернет тармоғидаги миллий сегментга мансуб сайтларни ривожлантириш муаммолари социологик тадқиқотлар ёрдамида очиб берилган ҳамда сайтлар мазмунини такомиллаштиришга таъсир этувчи бир қатор омиллар таснифланган.

Калит сўзлар: ахборот хавфсизлиги, жамоатчилик фикри, миллий сегмент, миллий сайтлар, сўровнома, ахборот майдони, веб-сайт, ижтимоий тармоқлар, интернет журналистикаси, дизайн, интерфаоллик.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается деятельность национального сегмента сети Интернет в эпоху информатизации общества и анализируются результаты его деятельности. При этом посредством социологических исследований выявляются проблемы развития информационных ресурсов в национальном сегменте сети Интернет, а также приводится и систематизируется ряд факторов, влияющих на эффективность наполняемости сайта актуальными материалами.

Ключевые слова: информационная безопасность, общественное мнение, национальный сегмент, национальные сайты, опрос, информационное пространство, сайт, социальные сети, интернет-журналистика, дизайн, интерактивность.

At the current stage of world development, the Internet network has emerged as an information and communication technology that unites humanity and is constantly developing. It should be noted that the speed of development of the Internet network in society is at a rapid level, and its social technical capabilities have generalized the possibilities and poten-

tial available in public, social group level and interpersonal communications. This situation requires the research of the social system, communicative features of the global Internet, by applying the methodology of scientific knowledge and sociological approach which is considered a global computer network in society. In such conditions, the analysis of a completely new so-

cio-technical, socio-communicative and socio-cultural situation, sociological characteristics, preparation of independent conclusions and proposals aimed at ensuring Internet security acquires a significant practical importance.

In the first quarter of the 21st century, as a result of the possibilities of computers, the revolution of scientific technology entered a new era. The possibilities of effective use of mobile phones, various gadgets, Internet communications have formed innovative thinking among the members of the society, as a result of such a process, regular adaptation and integration of vertical electronic systems to the society took place. Innovative changes in the field of modern information technologies have had a serious impact on social institutions, systemic relations and social processes, such situations have created an opportunity for sociological researchers to promote the integration of Uzbekistan society in global relations, into the structure of the post-industrial world through scientifically based ideas. In this regard, it should be noted that one of the characteristics of the new stage of development is the rapid development of the mass information and communication system. The technical and technological classification of the newly formed mass media networks confirms that they quickly overcome territorial and time limitations. Thanks to the unprecedented development of mass communication systems, for the first time in the history of mankind, information has risen to the level of a social resource that is necessary to a certain extent for a person.

Globalization of mass media and communications has taken place the experience of a person has been transformed due to its content, essence, the process of effective use of the communication system. Mass communication is both a tool that provides a person's attitude to existence and a source that brings innovative ideas to our consciousness. This attitude applies to all forms of mass media, primarily the cyber-internet, a global computer network¹. Internet networks and the national segment in it are of great practical importance for the society of Uzbekistan at the present time due to the fact that information and globalization formed the basis of the transformational processes in the society.

The Internet network, which was formed in the middle of the 20th century, was originally created as a means of communication, a communication system used in emergency situations. However, at the end of the 20th century, in the first quarter of the 21st century, the global Internet developed as an international computer communication network, which took advantage of the national communication system, and its high-level capabilities were demonstrated². That is why the activity of the Internet has become the focus of social and natural sciences, including sociology, as a subject of scientific research. The general impact of the Internet on social change is closely related to fundamental changes in society. This is characterized by the fact that the development of civil society in Uzbekistan continues, the country has entered a new stage of development. The global Internet network is gaining importance in ensuring the democratic content of reforms in our country, deep and rapid social changes, economic development, religious tolerance, inter-ethnic tolerance, strengthening the country's position in the international arena. As a result of this process, a radically updated information system was formed in Uzbekistan, and this situation created improved social relations.

The activation of the members of the society in the economic, spiritual, and social spheres is evident. In such conditions, there are certain shortcomings in the activity of social institutions that satisfy the demands and wishes of the public, they cannot satisfy the ever-growing social demands of the individual, such a situation is clearly manifested in the social spheres, that is, they have not developed to the level of intensive development in society. Such a situation is a sign of weakness in the institutional system of the transforming society.

It should be noted that a complex situation arose in the field of social communications in the end of the 20th century and in the first quarter of the 21st century. The main reason for this was the rapid introduction of information technologies and computers into social life as a result of the scientific and technical revolution. Also, this shift in social life is characterized by the increasing influence of innovative media, that is, the global Internet, a global computer

¹ Шевченко И.А. Политические интернет-технологии в трансформирующемся обществе: Автореф. дис. ...канд. полит. наук. Ставрополь, 2005. – С.3-6.

² Браславец Л.А. Интернет-сервисы социальных сетей в современной системе средств массовой информации. URL: <http://www.dissercat.com/content/Internet-servisy-sotsialnykh-setei-v-sovremennoi-sisteme-sredstv-massovoi-informatsii>.

network, on social relations in society. At the same time, in the process of increasing the effectiveness of the formation of the communication system, its existing shortcomings were also revealed. These shortcomings include the dissemination of unfounded information on the Internet, including the national segment, sites, filled with information that is far from daily and historical objectivity, and non-social information, and the publication of articles intended to negatively affect the formation of the social consciousness of Internet users.

The process of independent study of the direct impact of official and unofficial Internet communications on the mass audience, the sociological aspects of the social role in the conditions of the transforming society puts forward tasks of theoretical, methodological and practical importance. As Professor A.S. Duzhnikova noted, Internet blogs as an important means of social communication now influence the public, the formation of its social consciousness, its spiritual and moral world, and the formation of its political culture³.

The global Internet network has the ability to express the classic features of social systems in virtual content, national character. That's why in today's Uzbek society, the presence and expression of the elements of the social system in the physical and virtual world is being observed. Such a process increases the influence of the social situation of the Internet on social processes, especially the role of its informal communication systems in the society is evident. In this regard, in the current period, sociologists, on the basis of modern, innovative content methods, the specific characteristics of the activities of blogs and social networks on the Internet, and the need for their social and systematic analysis have arisen⁴.

The Internet is a complex socio-technical phenomenon, a reality, an integral element in the transforming society of Uzbekistan, and the understanding of its social importance suggests the task of approaching it from a sociological point of view. Therefore, it is important to study the role of official communications on the Internet, including the national segment, in the current democratic reforms, the impact of Internet

blogs and social communications on mass processes, as an important aspect of sociology.

Sociologist scientist M. Bekmurodov states that communication in the 21st century cannot be imagined without various mass dialogues and communication processes that connect and direct human activity, social and political life⁵.

Sociological analysis of the nature, function and social importance of the global Internet network, research of the content and goals of the social functions of the global computer network show that it has a direct impact on social systems, activities and processes of social institutions. In such conditions, it is appropriate to pay attention not only to the communicative functions of the Internet, but also to its social and cultural functions as a global network in society through a sociological approach. Especially in the process of scientific knowledge, epistemologically, social and systemic changes in the Internet world play an important role. At the same time, it is appropriate to pay attention to the changes in the structure of everyday social reality outside the global Internet information network. Such a process, in turn, confirms that the influence of the global information system on social processes in the society of Uzbekistan is increasing under the conditions of a new stage of development. Nowadays, the Internet is a multi-domain system. According to sociologists, there are several ways to evaluate the activities of Internet classification types. This system is mainly divided into formal and informal communication systems. The first group includes information, news sites, portals, Internet resources of various contents and directions, as a copy of mass media in the virtual world. Blogger communities belong to the second group.

Effective use of opportunities of the virtual world in social networks, Internet forums, chats, interpersonal and group communication has a nationwide character⁶. The difficulty, complexity, and constant changes of the elements of the Internet information space in the sociological research of the social situation of the Internet network are related to the interaction of official and unofficial sites. In this regard, it should be

³ Дужникова А. С. Социальные сети: современные тенденции и типы пользования // Мониторинг. 2010. №5 (99). URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sotsialnye-seti-sovremennye-tendentsii-i-tipy-polzovaniya>.

⁴ Асеева О. В. Социологический анализ социальной активности молодежи в сетевых сообществах Интернет // СИСП. 2011. №4. URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sotsiologicheskii-analiz-sotsialnoy-aktivnosti-molodezhi-v-setevykh-soobshchestvah-internet>.

⁵ Моррис М., Оган С. Интернет как масс-медиа // Журнал-коммуникации. 1996. № 1.

⁶ Бекмуродов М. Замонавий бошқарув социологияси: Монография. – Тошкент: “Ёшлар”, 2020. – 420-б.

noted that social communications operate in different forms on the global Internet. In this process, as a special type of Internet communication, blogs took one of the leading places. The introduction of blogs in the Internet creates conditions for a person to demonstrate his communicative abilities, as well as to show, confirm, and present himself in the virtual world of his intellectual thoughts from a social and cultural point of view. Blogs are an important presentation of socio-linguistics, a unique socio-cultural phenomenon, a reality, the study of their nature, development trends creates conditions for the identification of new aspects of the cultural transformation of public opinion on a scientific basis. "Blog industry differs from other sites by its specific structure, and is distinguished by the interrelationship of different bloggers, audience influence, that is, the number of listeners, general popularity, and communicative respect"⁷.

In the new stage of development, Internet communities connected to the global network are playing an important role in the society of Uzbekistan. Their activity as an integrated element in society led to communicative cultural changes. Network Internet communities have had a significant impact on the social maturity and socialization process of the young generation, on the system of human life relationships, social psychological, and social cultural and political views.

Internet communities have a serious impact on social processes in society, socialization of young people, change people's way of life, social-spiritual and social-cultural skills. During the new stage of development of the Internet community, the individual as a phenomenon of information communication culture replaces the practice of virtual daily life. Actions related to information exchange, conversation, finding a new job, personal interest, developing a hobby, and increasing social activity are transferred to the page of the global Internet network. As a result of such a process, new social structural forms are created within the framework of virtual reality, but which have a serious impact on the physical situation.

Communicative Internet communities in the global Internet network, that is, blogs and social networks, are directly related to the methodological and methodical problems of the informal national segment, the dialectical opposition of the physical world and

the virtual world. The main difficulty in this process is that when the researcher considers the physical reality during the analysis, the object of research is the content of the virtual world and in most cases has an anonymous, indirect character. At the same time, the use of sociological researches and their results, their application to human practical activities is of great importance. Such a process, under the conditions of a new stage of development, requires conducting new research works and empirical observations on the topic of various aspects of the practice of virtual social structural elements.

Blogs and social networks occupy an important place in the life of the society of Uzbekistan in the new stage of development and have a multifaceted influence on social processes. They are especially common among young people, and other segments of the population are also familiar with informal Internet communications through the activities of blogs on social networks. Active participation in the field of social networks and blogs has a complementary nature, it is important to satisfy the social demands of Uzbekistan's population, it has an active influence on the surrounding environment, it demonstrates the individual and intellectual potential of a person, because such opportunities cannot be obtained in practice, in the social and economic spheres. As a result of their activity in the social network, blogs have the opportunity to influence the social, economic, and spiritual spheres of the society of Uzbekistan.

The study of the content and essence of the theoretical and methodological bases of the activity of the national segment in ensuring the security of the Internet requires an understanding of the social structural and communicative features of the global Internet computer network, which is directly related to the new stage of development. In this process, for a person who actively participates in democratic reforms, that is, in the process of forming his socialized thinking, ensuring internet security and independent analysis of the theoretical and methodological aspects of the activity of the national segment becomes practical and decisive. The results of the research confirm that the role of the activity of the national segment of the Internet in social processes and the socialization of young people is increasing in the new stage of development.

⁷ Судич Ю.В., Проказин В.В. Роль социальных сетей в жизни молодежи. URL: <http://sibac.info/11367>.

Based on the analyzes conducted in this direction, the following conclusions and recommendations are put forward:

First of all, despite the difference between blogs and social networks, which exist in the national segment of the world Internet network, they have a similar character, the scale of information dissemination through them, that is, the geography and generality of the affected audience. That is why there should not be monitoring of blogs and social networks by state organizations;

second, the fact that blogs and social networks on the world Internet are not controlled by state organizations is related to the freedom of speech in the country, the fact that the Internet is a global, worldwide network, and its confidential possibilities. Therefore, as a result of the fact that Internet sites are not controlled in Uzbekistan, it creates conditions for the further development of the national segment;

third, the need to strengthen the position of national segments in the Internet network, to ensure its

security, the specific influence of some Internet blogs on public opinion, the attitude of the population of Uzbekistan to events of social and economic content, their assessment, directly affects the socio-political, socio-cultural situation;

fourth, the freedom of existing blogs to receive news, to transmit to the audience, the content of blog publications and articles through national internet segments can affect the existing system of social problems, the solution of conflict situations;

fifth, blogs in the national segment of the Internet can become a source of incorrect, negative information, as they may not agree with the opinions of the mass media operating in the country. Therefore, in order to ensure the security of information on the Internet, it is necessary to take into account the communicative, social, and cultural process that exists in society and its transformation, and it is appropriate to conduct sociological surveys among users in order to understand the place of blogs and social networks in the world Internet network system, to study the directions of their activities.

